

Diversity of Grasshoppers (Acrididae) In Different Habitats of Shahuwadi Tahsil, and Boundaries of Ratnagiri District (Maharashtra)

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Abstract:

The grasshoppers are included in class insecta of phylum Arthropoda. The reach diversity and species reaches of grasshoppers is seen in the month of September and October. The grasshoppers are voracious feeders. Grasshoppers are playing very important role in grassland ecosystem. Life cycle of grasshoppers shows complete metamorphosis. The stages of life cycle include namely- Egg, Nymph and Adult. To protect from predators grasshoppers shows camouflage mechanism. Grasshoppers are voracious eater and mostly damage to agricultural crops like rice, maize, vegetables etc. This study was undertaken from May 2023 to May 2024 in different habitats of Shahuwadi Tahsil of Kolhapur district and boundaries of Ratnagiri district.

Keywords: Grasshoppers, Ecosystem, Nymph, Arthropoda, Predator

Introduction:

The grasshopper family Acrididae is one of the most diverse lineages within Orthoptera, including more than 6,700 valid species distributed worldwide. Grasshoppers are dominant herbivores, which have diversified into grassland, desert, semi-aquatic, alpine, and tropical forest habitats, and exhibit a wide array of morphological, ecological, and behavioral diversity.

The present study on grasshopper diversity was carried out in different habitats of Shahuwadi Tahsil and boundaries of Ratnagiri district of Maharashtra state. The short horned grasshoppers were collected from these areas during the May 2023 to May 2024. Different areas were chosen with the intension of survey amongst different habitats which includes open grasslands, bushy vegetation with grass land patches, bushy, shrubby areas, ground surfaces and agricultural areas, forest areas. Species diversity of grasshoppers is depend on climatic conditions. Some climatic factors such as temperature, humidity, rainfalls

influence grasshopper species diversity. The grasshoppers choose grasses according to their body colours to protect from enemies.

Materials and Methods:

Grasshoppers were collected from different habitats using sweeping net in the morning and evening time. The collection was done during May-2023 to May-2024. Collected specimens were brought to laboratory and processed for dry preservation. The specimens were first relaxed, pinned, labelled, stretched on stretching box and left for 72 h to prevent decomposition. The specimens were sorted out into different taxonomic groups. The collected grasshoppers were identified using the book Fauna of British India (Kirby, 1914) and also by referring to the web pages namely, <http://bugguide.net> and <http://www.orthoptera.org>.

Study Area:

Grasshopper diversity was studied at different habitats of Shahuwadi Tahsil and

boundries of Ratnagiri district. This places are located in the foot hills of Sayhadri Ghat and with deciduous and semi evergreen forest. Shauwadi Tahsil is geographically situated at 11.0398° N Latitude and

76.8788° E Longitude. The study area was divided into different habitats namely, grasslands, shrubs, agricultural area, forest area and human altered area.

Table 1. The Grasshoppers diversity of different habitats of Shahuwadi Tahsil

Sr.No.	Sampling habitats	Species	Family	Subfamily	Tribe
1	Grasslands	<i>Cruciotacris decisa</i>	Acrididae	Gomphocerinae	Arcypterini
		<i>Acrotylus insubricus</i>	Acrididae	Oedipodinae	Acrotylini
		<i>Paropaon sp.</i>	Acrididae	Rhytidochrotinae	
		<i>Hieroglyphus nigrorepletus</i>	Acrididae	Hemiacridinae	Hieroglyphini
		<i>Angaracris barabensis</i>	Acrididae	Oedipodinae	
		<i>Atractomorpha crenulata</i>	Pyrgomorphidae	Pyrgomorphinae	Atractomorphin
		<i>Tagsta indica</i>	Pyrgomorphidae	Pyrgomorphinae	Tagastin
		<i>Chrotogonus oxypterus</i>	Pyrgomorphidae	Pyrgomorphinae	Chrotogonini
		<i>Hieroglyphus oryzivorus</i>	Acrididae	Hemiacridinae	Hieroglyphini
		<i>Eucoptacra praemorsa</i>	--	Coptacrinae	
2	Agricultural Area	<i>Gastrimargus africanus</i>	Acrididae	Oedipodinae	Locustin
		<i>Acrotylus humbertianus</i>	Acrididae	Oedipodinae	Acrotylin
		<i>Chrotogonus turanicus</i>	Pyrgomorphidae	Pyrgomorphinae	Chrotogonini
		<i>Hieroglyphus nigrorepletus</i>	Acrididae	Hemiacridinae	Hieroglyphini
		<i>Spathosternum prasiniferum</i>		Spathosterninae	Spathosternini
3	Shurbby area	<i>Acrida exaltata</i>	Acrididae	Acridinae	Acridini
		<i>Cyrtacanthacris tartarica</i>	Acrididae	Cyrtacanthacridinae	Cyrtacanthacridini
		<i>Acrida gigantea</i>	Acrididae	Acridinae	Acridini
		<i>Chrotogonus oxypterus</i>	Pyrgomorphidae	Pyrgomorphinae	Chrotogonini
		<i>Atractomorpha psittacina</i>	Pyrgomorphidae	Pyrgomorphinae	Atractomorphini
		<i>Trilophidia anulata</i>	Acrididae	Oedipodinae	Trilophidiini
4	Forest Area	<i>Sphingonotus longipennis</i>	Acrididae	Oedipodinae	Sphingonotin
		<i>Eyprepocnemis alacris</i>	Acrididae	Eyprepocnemidinae	Eyprepocnemidini
		<i>Oxya fuscovittata</i>	Acrididae	Oxyinae	Oxyini
		<i>Catantops pinguis</i>	Acrididae	Catantopinae	Catantopini
		<i>Chrotogonus trachypterus</i>	Pyrgomorphidae	Pyrgomorphinae	Chrotogonini
		<i>Aulacobothrus luteipes</i> (Walker, 1871)	Acrididae	Gomphocerinae	Arcypterin
		<i>Hieroglyphus nigrorepletus</i>	Acrididae	Hemiacridinae	Hieroglyphini

Table 2. The Grasshoppers diversity of different habitats of boundaries of Ratnagiri District

Sr. No.	Sampling habitat	Species	Family	Subfamily	Tribe
1	Grasslands	<i>Atractomorpha crenulata</i>	Pyrgomorphidae	Pyrgomorphinae	Atractomorphin
		<i>Acrotylus insubricus</i>	Acrididae	Oedipodinae	Acrotylini
		<i>Angaracris barabensis</i>	Acrididae	Oedipodinae	
		<i>Oxya hyla intricata</i>	Acrididae	Oxyinae	Oxyini
		<i>Cruciotacris decisa</i>	Acrididae	Gomphocerinae	Arcypterini
		<i>Heteropternis respondens</i>	Acrididae	Oedipodinae	Epacromiini
2	Agricultural Area	<i>Spathosternum prasiniferum</i>	Acrididae	Spathosterninae	Spathosternini
		<i>Hieroglyphus banian</i>	Acrididae	Hemiacridinae	Hieroglyphini
		<i>Oedaleus seneglenis</i>	Acrididae	Oedipodinae	Locustini
		<i>Galidacris variabilis</i>	Acrididae	Rhytidochrotinae	
		<i>Chrotogonus oxypterus</i>	Pyrgomorphidae	Pyrgomorphinae	Chrotogonini
		<i>Abracris sp</i>	Acrididae	Ommatolampidinae	
		<i>Aiolopus simulatrix</i>	Acrididae	Oedipodinae	Epacromiini
		<i>Aiolopus thalassinus</i>	Acrididae	Oedipodinae	Epacromiini
		<i>Gastrimargus africanus</i>	Acrididae	Oedipodinae	Locustini
		<i>Hieroglyphus nigrorepletus</i>	Acrididae	Hemiacridinae	Hieroglyphini
		<i>Acrotylus humbertianus</i>	Acrididae	Oedipodinae	Acrotylini
3	Shurbby area	<i>Acrida exaltata</i>	Acrididae	Acridinae	Acridini
		<i>Oxya japonica japonica</i>	Acrididae	Oxyinae	Oxyini
		<i>Chrotogonus trachypterus</i>	Pyrgomorphidae	Pyrgomorphinae	Chrotogonini
		<i>Cyrtacanthacris tartarica</i>	Acrididae	Cyrtacanthacridinae	Cyrtacanthacridini
		<i>Oedaleus abruptus</i>	Acrididae	Oedipodinae	Locustini
4	Forest Area	<i>Sphingonotus longipennis</i>	Acrididae	Oedipodinae	Sphingonotini
		<i>Catantops pinguis</i>	Acrididae	Catantopinae	Catantopini
		<i>Hieroglyphus nigrorepletus</i>	Acrididae	Hemiacridinae	Hieroglyphini
		<i>Oxya japonica japonica</i>	Acrididae	Oxyinae	Oxyini
		<i>Acrida turrita</i>	Acrididae	Acridinae	Acridini
		<i>Truxalis indica</i>	Acrididae	Acridinae	Truxalini

Result and Discussions:

The checklist of Table 1 and 2 of grasshoppers is an outcome of field work carried out between months May 2023 to May 2024 which is strictly short horned grasshopper survey based on selected areas of Shahuwadin Tahsil and boundries of Ratnagiri district. 20 species documented were found to be present in various habitats studied grasslands, shrubby area, forest area and agricultural fields from Shahuwadi Tahsil and boundries or Ratnagiri district.

The present study shows that 26 species belongs to 14 different genera belonging to 2 families, 11 sub families and

14 tribes have been recoded (Table 1 and 2). was recorded. Families Acrididae (90%), and Pyrgomorphidae (10%) are confirm between the different habitats of Shahuwadin Tahsil and boundries of Ratnagiri district. whereas maximum species represented by subfamily Pyrgomorphinae(10), Oedipodinae (7) followed by Hemiacridinae(7), Oxyinae(03), , Acridinae(04), Catantopinae(02), Eyprepocnemidinae(01) and Spathosterninae(02) This study reported that the family Acididae of Grasshopper is having wide habitat preference.

Conclusion:

On the basis of this study we can conclude that different habitats of Shahuwadin Tehsil and boundaries of Ratnagiri district shows the variety of short horned grasshoppers belonging to phylum Orthoptera and family Acrididae. The continuous study from these areas will add the more numbers of species in the current list of the species. A long-term study needed to observe taxonomy, species richness and distribution in all seasons and their interaction with the environmental changes.

Conflicts of Interest:

Authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

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